

Plus Minus Voting

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

A method to collectively prioritize and compare a set of (brainstorm) activities or discussion points. It helps to focus on activities or discussion points of the highest interest of the group.

Benefits

An ideal method to make quick, yet democratic decisions when short on time, but having many topics to discuss. It ensures that all partners are included and heard in the decision-making.

Practical recommendations

Identification of options (10 min)

Write all discussion points, activities, ideas or whatever you would like to make a collective decision on, on separate cards or large post-its. This can be done with the entire group

Voting (5 min)

Each participant gets 3 'plus' (+) votes and 3 'minus' (-) votes. Participants are free in the way they distribute their votes amongst the options. They can put their 3 'plus' votes on one option or can distribute them amongst three distinct options.

Options with the most 'plus' votes and the least 'minus' votes win.

Decision-making (15-30 min)

Count the votes. Engage with the group in order to consolidate the final decision.

If there are any options which require further actions in the future - this is also the time to note this down.

This meeting format can be done offline and online, look for our suggestions for online whiteboards in the toolbox.

Applicability box

Main MA Skills supported

Work with a diversity of professional backgrounds

Transparent communication about agendas, expectations and results

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Plus Minus Voting by FunRetrospectives](#)

**right click to open*